

But zero tillage leaves intact the rice stubble that harbors hibernating *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *S. innotata*, and *Sesamia inferens* SB. The larvae carry over to the next rice crop. *Sesamia* sp. also attacks wheat, spring maize, and sugarcane.

We assessed the extent to which Basmati 370 rice stubble would remain in condition for infestation by hibernating SB larvae in four differently tilled wheat fields in 1984-85 and 1985-86. A 65-hp tractor and implements (cultivator, plank, rototiller, and seed drill) were used in tillage operations in 30- × 30-m plots at the adaptive research farm and on 3 farmers' fields. Stubble was collected from 4 randomly selected 3-m² areas of each tillage type — zero-tilled/direct-drilled; cultivator run twice followed by one planking; cultivator run three times followed by two plankings; rototiller once, cultivator

Effect of tillage on stubble destruction and rice SB larvae hibernation in wheat following rice.^a Sheikhpura, Pakistan.

Tillage operation	Stubble (no./3 m ²)	SB-infested stubble (%)	Larvae (no./stubble)	Destruction (%) of stubble
<i>1984-85</i>				
Zero-tilled ^b /direct-drilled	137 a	84 a	3.8 ab	0
Cultivator (2) + plank (1)	44 b	46 b	1.8 d	64
Cultivator (3) + plank (2)	26 c	5 d	0.7 ef	79
Rototiller (1) + cultivator (2) + plank (1)	1 e	0 e	0.0 f	99
<i>1985-86</i>				
Zero-tilled ^b /direct-drilled	138 a	83 a	2.9 be	0
Cultivator (2) + plank (1)	37 b	37 c	2.0 cd	70
Cultivator (3) + plank (2)	14 d	5 de	1.8 d	88
Rototiller (1) + cultivator (2) + plank (1)	0 e	0 e	0.0 f	99

^aFigures followed by common letters are not statistically different (95% level of confidence by DMRT). ^bNo land preparation carried out. Wheat seed directly drilled.

twice, and planking once. The stubble was dissected in the laboratory for number of SB larvae/ stubble.

Data reveal nearly 100% destruction of stubble and no hibernating SB larvae in the rototilled fields (see table).

Cultivating followed by planking was not as effective in stubble destruction, but its effectiveness increased with number of runs. Larvae infestation was highest in the stubble of zero-tilled/direct-drilled fields. □

Intercropping upland rice and Lamtoro in acid Red Yellow Podzolic soils

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We studied the interactions of four cultivars of Lamtoro *Leucaena leucocephala* with upland rice *Oryza sativa* cultivar Sentani in acid Red Yellow Podzolic soil during 1983-84 cropping season. The soil was classified Haplorthox - Paleudult, with a 0-27 cm clayey topsoil, with pH of 4.2, exchangeable Al+H and Ca+Mg 4.0 and 0.7 meq/100 g, and Al saturation 85%.

Three-month-old Lamtoro seedlings were planted in double hedgerows 2 m apart (see figure). Each double hedgerow was 50 cm apart, with 33.3 cm between plants. Triple superphosphate (TSP) at 200 kg/ha was applied at the bottom of the plant hole at planting. The plants were cut back to 30 cm above the ground 4 mo after planting

Planting arrangement of Lamtoro and upland rice. Sumatra, Indonesia, 1983-84.

and the biomass incorporated into the soil.

One month after cutting and incorporating Lamtoro, upland rice was interseeded at 25- × 25-cm spacing into the well-established Lamtoro rows. Then 200 kg TSP, 50 kg KCl, and 40 kg carbofuran/ha were applied at the bottom of the plant hole with rice seeds. Two additional cuttings of Lamtoro were made at 2-mo intervals after rice seeding.

The experiment with Lamtoro cultivars Peru, K-8, K-28, Gung, and control without Lamtoro was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Plot size was 5 × 5m.

After three cuttings, cumulative dry weight of biomass of Peru was 4.6 t, Gung 4.7 t, K-8 5.2t, K-28 6.3 t/ha (see table). However, the interactions between upland rice and Lamtoro did not appear to favor upland rice growth

and yield. At harvest, rice had a significant plant height reduction of 9-12% and tiller number reduction of 18-24%. The pure stand of upland rice yielded 2.8 t/ha; intercropped rice showed significant yield reduction. Reduced plant height, tiller number, and grain yield was correlated positively with

Lamtoro cumulative dry weight.

The results suggest a negative interaction between Lamtoro cultivars and intercropped upland rice with the 2 m row spacing. Row spacing should be adjusted for optimum rice yield.

A decrease in exchangeable A1+H and A1 saturation and an increase in

exchangeable Ca+Mg occurred in the intercropped plots. Intercropping upland rice and Lamtoro and returning Lamtoro biomass to the soil over a period of several years may actually result in decreased A1 and increased plant nutrients in the soil. □

Cumulative dry weight of Lamtoro after 3 cuttings, growth and yield of intercropped upland rice, and soil chemical properties after rice harvest.^a Sumatra, Indonesia, 1983-84.

Lamtoro variety	Cumulative dry weight (t/ha)	Upland rice plant height (cm)			Upland rice tillers (no./hill)			Upland rice grain yield (t/ha)	Exchangeable A1+H (meq/100 g)	Exchangeable Ca+Mg (meq/100 g)	A1 saturation (%)
		30 DAS	60 DAS	Harvest	30 DAS	60 DAS	Harvest				
Peru	4.6 a	43 a	73 a	111 c	19 a	34 a	13 b	2.1 b	3.9 ab	0.8 a	82 ab
K-8	5.2 a	45 a	74 a	120 ab	20 a	37 a	14 b	2.4 b	3.8 ab	0.8 a	82 ab
K-28	6.3 a	47 a	76 a	120 ab	18 a	38 a	14 b	1.7 c	2.8 b	1.5 b	63 b
Gung	4.7 a	41 a	69 a	115 bc	17 a	39 a	14 b	2.1 b	3.5 ab	0.9 a	84 a
Control	-	42 a	79 a	126 a	21 a	36 a	17 a	2.8 a	4.0 a	0.7 a	85 a

^aDAS = days after seeding. Data are means of 4 replications. Mean separation by DMRT at 5%.

Performance of transplanted aman rice varieties in cropping pattern trials

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We evaluated six T. aman rice varieties in cropping pattern trials in the 1982-1983 late wet seasons. The Hathazari cropping systems site is medium high land. The objective was to identify short-duration varieties with higher yields at low fertilizer levels in the broadcast aus - T. aman - cowpea cropping pattern under rainfed conditions.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with five replications across farms. Each year, 37-d-old seedlings were transplanted 24-27 Aug at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 60-17.6-16.6 kg NPK/ha.

The varieties exhibited significant variations in yield, days to flowering, and days to maturity (see table).

BR11 is resistant to lodging and shattering, with medium grains. Its market value is higher because its grains produce quality rice and pop. □

Performance of T. aman varieties in farmers' cropping patterns at Hathazari, Bangladesh, 1982-83.^a

Variety	Flowering (DT)		Maturity (DT)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1982	1983	1982	1983	1982	1983
BR3	68 b	70 ab	109 b	112 b	3.2 a	3.5 ab
BR4	65 c	67 bc	106 bc	109 bc	2.6 ab	3.0 b
BR10	64 c	66 c	106 bc	108 c	3.2 a	3.4 b
BR11	62 d	64 c	101 c	108 c	3.2 a	4.3 a
Pajam	56 e	59 d	97 d	101 d	2.8 a	2.7 b
Chakkal (check)	72 a	73 a	114 a	117 a	2.0 b	2.8 b
CV (%)	2.7	4.6	2.9	2.1	19.8	20.0

^aDT = days after transplanting.

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Production

Economics of rice gall midge (GM) management in resistant and susceptible cultures

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We studied the incidence of GM in three resistant and one GM-susceptible cultivars with and without pest management in a split-plot design with three replications during the 1986 wet season.

GM incidence in the susceptible variety crossed the economic threshold (ETL) 48 d after transplanting (DT)